

INTERCHARACTER CONFLICT AND SOCIAL CONFLICT

Khamidova M.O.

Professor, Department of Preschool and Primary Education, Namangan State University

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Abstract. *The role of artistic literature in our society is unparalleled. Artistic works are considered the main means of shaping and enriching a person's moral world. Especially in today's literature, the new worldview and the colorful facets of human thought are reflected. This article thoroughly examines the intercharacter conflict and social conflict in the novel "Olaboji" by the People's Writer of Uzbekistan, Shukur Kholmirezayev.*

Keywords: *national characters, talented author, tendency, heroes' worldviews, artistic analysis, artistic image, artistic intent, creative process, national traditions, writer's imagination, heroes' inner world, intercharacter conflict, social conflict, artistic skill, individual style.*

The outstanding representative of modern Uzbek prose, Shukur Kholmirezayev, entered the literary scene at the end of the 1950s. From the very beginning of his creative journey, he depicted aspects of life that were close and familiar, striving for sincerity in his descriptions and paying special attention to the analysis of his characters' inner worlds. He began to refine his style.

As is known, style is the aesthetic unity of figurative-expressive details in a literary work, manifesting the writer's individuality in the use of artistic depiction methods. Style, as literary scholar S. Mamajonov emphasized, is the individuality of the writer visible in the unity of "perception" and "expression." "Individual style," as noted by literary scholar N. Shukurov, "is the way the author perceives reality in their own unique manner" [3, 126]. However, style is not merely a dry arithmetic sum of the artistic depiction methods in a work, but rather the harmonious integration of these methods, serving to express the idea and reveal the character of the protagonist.

Individual style is a collection of the author's poetic thinking and the distinctive features noticeable in their expression of life. Style is the result of the writer's active engagement with the events and phenomena of their time, serving as a key factor that demonstrates the originality of the creator and distinguishes them from other writers. The more talented the writer, the more vividly their style will manifest. Only an author with their own style can be a true artist.

In Shukur Kholmirezayev's novel *Olaboji*, the injustices, immorality, and spiritual corruption that pervade life are masterfully depicted. The events of the novel take place in Olatogh district of Surkhandarya region during the 1980s, mainly over a period of ten to fifteen days. Despite this short timeframe, the novel provides a vivid portrayal of nearly a century of our people's history, filled with events and distortions. The author sharply criticizes the falsification of history, the occupation of Central Asia by the Tsarist Empire, and the trampling of national customs during the depiction of the novel's events.

The main character of *Olaboji* is Ulton Sultonov, who lives in one of the mountain villages. After graduating from Tashkent State University, he works first as a journalist for the district newspaper and later as a teacher at his village school. He leads a modest life. One day, he is summoned by the first secretary of the district party committee, Tolliboy Kuchkorov, who gives him an important task. He is ordered to inspect the school in Oqsuv together with Bahor, the chief physician of the village hospital. This process brings the two young people closer together, leading to their eventual marriage under the secretary's guidance within a week. [5, 89] However, their

happiness does not last even three days. Soon, the true nature of this “pure service” is revealed. The secretary's “pure service” conceals a vile purpose. By marrying Bahor off, the district leader aims to hide his secret and continue his indulgence. Once the secret is exposed, the secretary resorts to violence. He drives the groom insane and has him committed to a mental hospital.

Due to this injustice, the pure-hearted and honorable Ulton Sultonov ultimately rises against the hypocrisy and lies surrounding him. No one understands or supports him. The young man, with his pure heart and good intentions, becomes alienated from his own homeland, finding himself in a state of *olaboji* (displacement).

In the novel, alongside the characters of Ulton Sultonov, Tokliboy Kuchkorov, and Bahor, vivid portrayals of the district party committee's second secretary Tarakanov, the village director Butaboy Sopiyeu, the chairman of the village council Tursuntosh, the party secretary Makhfirat Egamkulova, Zikriyo domla, the hardworking, honorable, and simple shepherd Sultan bobo, are created. The author skillfully utilizes the possibilities of psychological depiction to reveal the characters' traits. The main characters in the novel differ significantly from one another in terms of their internal and external worlds.

In *Olaboji*, the unity of nature and society, as well as the “mysteries” of the animal world, are also reflected. The author masterfully describes the nature of Surkhandarya region, effectively and appropriately using it to unveil the novel's theme. In this, Shukur Kholmirezayev's distinctive style is clearly evident [5, 60].

Shukur Kholmirezayev's novel *Olaboji* is built on the development of the worlds of good and evil. The realm of goodness is represented by Ulton, Ashim (Koraboy), Khurram, Tursuntosh (Tursunoy), Abdukayum, Dunyo, and Kobil, while the realm of evil is expressed through the actions of Tokliboy Kuchkorov, Bahor, Butaboy Sopiyeu, Tarakanov, and Makhfirat Egamkulova.

The novel possesses a polyphonic quality. It explores all the negative aspects and maladies of a totalitarian societal system. This condition persists from the first page of the work to its conclusion.

The novel begins with Ulton, an archaeologist by profession but recognized as a journalist, who has returned to his village in recent years to teach natural sciences at school. He is known for his hunting skills and lives alone in an extraordinary hut built on pillars. The story kicks off when the first secretary of the district committee, Tokliboy Kuchkorov, invites him. Thus, the reader becomes acquainted with the main character of the novel. The author does not provide a straightforward description of Ulton's personality, as seen in some works; instead, it reveals itself through the events and contrasts he faces. Each event related to his activities unveils human virtues and individuality. Beneath these events social and political issues lie.

Ulton's thoughts wander as he arrives at the collective farm under the special assignment of the director Butaboy Sopiyeu. When he reaches the district committee, he is warmly welcomed by his former teacher, now the secretary of the district committee, Tokliboy Kuchkorov. After some jokes and light banter, they start discussing the school. Despite the school director Zokir Urinov having written about the school's dilapidated condition everywhere, no one seemed to pay attention. However, the secretary's interest in school greatly pleases Ulton. Furthermore, the secretary states: “The reason for calling you is this: I trust you... You will visit your school as a representative of the district committee, check everything, and write down all its deficiencies... And in these five days, think about what can be done” [10, 30].

As we know, the issue of schools has always been a pressing matter, and it remains so today. The attention of a high-ranking official towards it indicates that he is a good person. Therefore, Tokliboy Kuchkorov leaves an impression as such a person among us.

The doctor, Bahor, who is called along with Ulton, is told, "You will determine whether the school meets the hygiene and sanitation requirements," and both are sent to check the school. This situation seems unusual to Ulton. After all, there are responsible organizations that oversee the school's operations! Why must Ulton and Bahor, who is overwhelmed with work, be the ones to conduct this check? Ulton will find the answer to this troubling question by the end of the narrative.

The author does not merely describe events; instead, he directs everything toward a purpose. This particular event serves three objectives: to reveal the identities of the active characters, to attract the attention of the relevant authorities regarding the school issue, and to create a foundation for bringing Ulton and Bahor closer together.

Tokliboy Kuchkorov's actions initially evoke goodwill; he is energetic, cheerful, inclined towards poetry, and engages in creative endeavors himself. In every conversation, he cites examples from Mashrab's ghazals and shares wise thoughts. Importantly, he does not separate himself from people; he treats everyone equally. At first glance, he appears to be an exemplary leader.

Ulton asked, "How are you, teacher?" Tokliboy Kuchkorov replied, "Who says I'm 'bad'? Is it Zokir Urinov? I know," he said, laughing heartily as he sat beside the chair. "Who can say anything good about the raykom secretary? Who?" He delighted in his question, then turned away. "No one! When he reached his revolving chair, he sat up straight and said, 'The scholar is proud of knowledge, the ignorant is immersed in rebellion. Who knows whose stone will fall short on the Day of Judgment?'" "Well, how is it?" he asked [9, 11].

In the novel, there are many aspects that showcase Tokliboy Kuchkorov's appealing traits. From the beginning until the last pages of the work, he is portrayed as a good person who understands the injustices occurring in society, and due to a lack of freedom to oppose them, readers feel pity for his "tragedy." However, throughout the reading process, the reader's positive opinion about him gradually turns negative. He even stoops to sending Ulton to a psychiatric hospital to cover up his own actions.

Ulton's "madness" was substantiated by a report written by Bahor. Even while writing, it was done very professionally. The psychiatrist Berdiqul was a person who had not lost his conscience and genuinely understood the "madmen" lying here, feeling deeply affected by their fates. Because of this, he correctly understood Ulton's tragedy and did not regard him as mad. Berdiqul created an opportunity for Ulton to escape from this place. Ulton tried to eliminate the main "conductor" of the world of depravity. He hid a sawn-off shotgun in his coat and went to the raykom building. He fired twice at Tokliboy Kuchkorov, who was coming out of there. However, nothing happened to him because the barrel of the gun was cut off, causing the shot to scatter. Ulton was unable to achieve his goal because, in the socialist regime, the world of depravity had long and powerful hands. The novel concludes: "After Ulton was sent to the madrasah (the building of the psychiatric hospital was previously a madrasah, so people referred to it as such), Ashim received news one or two times. Once, when he brought warm clothes, Dr. Berdi said, 'Don't come here anymore.' But this surprised people: a bear-like creature appeared in the orphanage. Its walk resembled that of a bear: it walked hunched over, grunting and growling.

Occasionally, it came close to the city, sitting on top of a cave... When young children played around, their mothers frightened them with a single word: ‘Olaboji is coming!’”

This conclusion has two meanings. The first is that the world of depravity has turned a righteous, truthful, and natural person into “Olaboji.” The second is that society itself is built on the foundation of depravity, thus genuinely fears “Olaboji.” Because truth is powerful, it ultimately prevails. The idea stemming from the events of the work is based on this.

The artistic representation of reality by the writer Sh. Kholmirezayev, through artistic images and imaginative thinking, has been analyzed in relation to his creative and spiritual activities based on the historical category of artistry. This process changes in accordance with the spiritual and aesthetic needs of each era and the artistic taste. The issues of the event being a part of artistic reality, and the study of the harmony between form and content ensuring the work’s holistic organic unity have been explored. Attention has been given to the nature of the unreal world, which resembles external reality, the aesthetic subjectivity of the artistic text directed towards the reader, and the recreation of the unique phenomenon of artistic reality by the reader. By envisioning the spiritual and emotional state of the word artist during creative moments, an effort has been made to understand the multilayered meanings, particularly emphasizing that in the novel, the world is a concrete environment where a person acts, and that an educated person is always closely connected to human and worldly problems.

Thus, the attitude of the author towards the characters in the novel serves as a foundation for the artistic integrity, conditionality, reader orientation, originality, and universality of artistic principles, manifested in the subject-object-addressee unity, and allows for the observation of how the state of catharsis occurs in the reader and the instances of artistic emergence.

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